

CONDITIONS OF SERVICE AS CORRELATE OF TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN ONITSHA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

Enwezor Chibuogwu Helenⁱ

Department of Educational Foundations,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University,
Igbariam, Anambra State,
Nigeria

Abstract:

This paper investigated the conditions of service as correlate of teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria. The study was guided by four research questions and one hypothesis. The study employed survey research design. The area of study was Onitsha South local government area, Anambra state. The population of study consisted of all the 40 Head Teachers and 309 teachers in 40 primary schools found in Onitsha South local government area, Anambra state. The total population was 349. The sample size of the study consists of the 40 Head Masters and 180 teachers randomly selected through stratified simple random sampling method from the total population of 349. The total size for the study is 220. The researcher used a self-developed instrument for collecting the data for 20-item questionnaires titled, "Conditions of Service as Correlate of Teachers Job Performance in Primary Schools" (CSCTJPPS). The data collected were analyzed with descriptive statistics by mean statistics. The findings of the study showed that salary and promotion as conditions of services do not correlate with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria. The study concluded that higher salary and promotion of teachers in primary schools can satisfy them but may not improve pupils' academic achievement nor exert teachers to put more efforts in return to compensation for higher salaries. Also, regular increase of primary school teachers' salaries may not worth the investment they made on the children. The study, therefore, recommended among other things: teachers should be motivated inwardly to teach and improving their job performance not only waiting to be driven by external forces such as salary, promotion, housing provision and as well as medical care. This will better improve the teachers' job performance and pupils' academic performance in primary schools, especially in the study area and Nigeria in general. Also, government of Nigeria and Anambra state should encourage teachers in primary schools through

ⁱ Correspondence: email chiogewino@yahoo.com

adequate conditions of service in order to upgrade education system and educational output.

Keywords: teachers' job performance, primary schools, conditions of service

1. Introduction

In any society and nation today, attention is given to education. This is because education is the foundation and frontier of human and societal development. No education, no development. It is the bedrock of a country's national defense, improves the standard of living of people, industrialization and the grass root for morals and child development. In fact, it is clearly stated in the national policy objective on education that education is the instrument for sustainable socioeconomic development and social change as well as a vital instrument for the promotion of a progressive and united Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2016). This implies that without regard to education a nation is bound to remain undeveloped.

The quality of education is the country's refined poverty, inequalities, health improvement and enhancing the general well-being of persons. The level of development in any society is determined by the well-organized, managed and supervised education system. According to Osinubi (2007), a meaningful education system is a channel that transformed the world into a global community through the advancement of science and technology. Globally, education is regarded as a veritable instrument for the achievements of national goals. Education gives national direction and any nation that wants to achieve development indicators must invest, maintain and promote education administrators as well as teachers. It is fundamental to the development of every nation, and to a large extent, dictates the likely pattern of the other sectors while at the same time providing an insight into the nation's future, National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016). Education helps to develop individuals physically, mentally, socially and technologically to enable them to function effectively in any environment in which they may find themselves (Karaba, 2008).

No nation can afford to pay lip service to the education of its people; therefore various societies put a lot of capital on it to ensure that the entire generation acquires the necessary skills, knowledge and the desired attitudes critical for future survival of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2016). The degree of relationship between the government and the teachers in primary schools in Nigeria matters a lot in terms of salary payment, benefits and other conditions of service. Thus, conditions of service can be defined as the terms and conditions guiding employment contracts. The terms must go down well with parties involved (employer and employee).

According to Kornblumt (1997), conditions of service is described as legal agreements between a service provider or employer and an employee who wants to use or render the service. The person must agree to abide by the terms of service in order to use or offer the service. Seniwoliba (2013) sees conditions of service as that general

requirements, necessities and desirable factors that tend to make the working environment conducive and favourable and thus enhance worker's performance. There are various components of conditions of service which can affect teacher's performance in primary schools, and these include salary, status, working conditions, promotion, fringe benefits, job security and involvement in decision-making. The conditions service may include salary structure, allowance, dress code, duration of vacation, work hours, break policies, promotion, work-related responsibilities and number of sick days. It can also encompass certain benefits such as retirement plans and health insurance coverage. Luthans (2005) added that condition of service is in form of salary increment, gratuity, regular promotion, ensuring job security, and establishing cordial relationship among teachers. It is a contract that states that an employee is given employment for a certain length of time so long as the employee does not violate the terms of the contract. Workers with more valuable workplace skills are more likely to be able to negotiate better employment conditions.

In other hand, a teacher can be seen as a person who helps students to acquire knowledge, competence or virtue. According to Osei (2011), a teacher is defined as a *“person with the responsibility of training and educating members of any given society towards the acquisition of desired: knowledge, values, ideologies and skills for the benefit of the society”*. A teacher in a formal institution is expected to possess requisite qualification and qualities relevant to execute teaching practice effectively, so as to instill in the products the desired knowledge and skills. More so, conditions under which teachers work matters a lot, because it helps to bring out best practices from them. Teachers job performance is the measurement of the extent to which goals of national policy on education is realized. Eferakeya (1998) defined teachers' job performance as determining the degree to which teachers' orientations and classroom instructions contribute effectively towards the achievement of educational goals, and thereby becoming very helpful and profitable. Ijaiya (1991) sees teachers' performance as *“the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes”*.

Rao and Kumar (2004) observed that performance of teachers mainly depends on the teacher characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness; the pupils' characteristics such as opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom phenomena such as environment and climate, and organization and management.

Verspoor (2014) found that teachers are the initiators, facilitators of teaching and learning activities. They act as agent of change in any school system because of the roles they perform, they can be regarded as the heart of quality improvement strategy. The teachers normally perform better if conducive working environment is provided for them. The working condition may not be with a fat and higher salary structure, but improved in order to motivate teachers for high performance. George and Jones (2008) opined that teachers job dissatisfaction on the basis of working condition can lead to change of attitudes like; exhibiting aggressive behaviour towards pupils and co-teachers,

absenteeism from school with or without permission, boycotting of work, burn-out and early exits which will adversely affect pupils' academic performance negatively since its agreed that pupils achievement is a function of the teachers' input in the classroom.

To arrest this scenario, it is relevant for government to identify those ingredients of conditions of service that can enhance teachers' job satisfaction. Nobody works without having in mind to earn wages or salary to meet his or her personal needs. Therefore, better salaries and prompt payment motivate the entire teachers to put in their best in the classroom to improve pupils' performance. Bell (2012) maintained that, "*of all conditions of service, salary is the best predictor of teachers' job performance and productivity*". She found that job that offers higher salary would attract more and better qualified personnel than anyone that offers a lower pay. In Nigeria, salaries paid to teachers are insufficient, making it challenging for them to attend to their basic needs of life. By implication, teachers' salaries in both federal and state government cannot be compared with the salaries of other workers in the same cadre and the same qualifications as well as experience in other sectors of Nigerian economy like doctors, nurses, lawyers etc.

Thus, the extent to which primary educational goal is achieved depends basically on the teachers' productive output measured by pupils. Ogundele (2000) opined that "*no nation rises above the level of its education and no educational system outgrows the quality and status of its teachers*". But today in Nigeria, other sectors are riding over the teachers that taught them at the grass root level (primary school) in terms of jumbo salary, prompt payment, recognition, allowance, motivation, promotion, fringe benefits, staff development and terminal benefits. Furthermore, while other teachers work in order to satisfy their needs in life, others are constantly agitating for one thing or the other, which is a sign of lack of job satisfaction. This development has warranted teachers over the years to form union such as National Union of Teachers demanding for the improvement of conditions of service and better salary scales for teachers in primary schools in Nigeria. In the same vain, the state and federal governments stated that the current economic challenges and available government revenue cannot accommodate such demand for increasing salaries, allowances terminal benefits and improvements in the conditions service. However, they lay claims and accusations that teachers in primary schools are lazy, lack diligence and zeal to duty and their level of performance, efficiency and effectiveness do not merit such demand for increase in salary structure and better working conditions.

In the work of Venkatesh and Davis (2000) on the theory of action relating to reasons, teachers are willing to put in their best at work, but poor working conditions are the perceived factors of their low performance. Many primary school pupils in Onitsha South Local Government Area cannot read nor write accurately and based on this fact, teacher performance in those primary schools in the state and Nigeria in general cannot yield the result of achieving the primary education goals. The job performance of teachers in teaching profession is evaluated by relating teachers' attitudes with their duties and responsibilities required of them within the school and this is relevant in the formulation of education policies and realization of set educational goals (Neckermann and Kosfeld,

2008). According to Akuoko and Donkor (2012), added that the job performance of teachers in any educational level is measured by using performance rating scale or appraisal as found in civil service organizations such as; teachers' productive outputs seen in pupils performance, pedagogy, extra-activities for pupils, teacher-pupil relationship, changing teaching/learning process, use of instructional aids, improvisation of instructional aids, participation in extra curriculum activities, mastery of subject area, teacher-teacher relationship, above all, pupils' academic achievements. It is on this background that the researcher seeks to investigate conditions of service as correlate of teachers' job performance in primary schools using Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria, as a case study.

3. Statement of the Problem

It is a reality that teacher is the instrument through which education' objectives can be achieved. If teacher is properly motivated by the conditions of service, they would be satisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their pupils. Despite all, teachers' salaries in Anambra state cannot be compared with those of their counterparts in other sectors and most time what is given to them cannot meet their basic needs of life. The teachers in primary schools have to seek for alternative means to make ends meet, causing divided attention, absenteeism from school, irregular attendance to class, lack of concentration, dissatisfaction and among others. Ukeje (2007), opined that the rate of turnover of teachers' is decreasing at the alarming rate and those at work are embarking on frequent strikes for better conditions of service. This is why teachers' job performance in primary schools in Anambra state has to be questioned because of the poor academic performance of pupils in common entrance examination and lack of moral development in pupils.

Studies have shown that all the investigated causes of declined in teachers' job performance include; head teachers communication style, inadequate teacher development and interpersonal relationship amongst others (Akande, 2014; Ali & Ahmed, 2009). It is in view of this, that this study tends to examine conditions of service as correlate of teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

3.1 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate conditions of service as correlate of teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

- 1) To find out whether salary correlates with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.
- 2) To examine relationship between promotion and teachers job performance primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

- 3) To examine the influence of housing provision on teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.
- 4) To evaluate the effect of medical care on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

3.2 Research Question

- 1) How does salary correlate with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?
- 2) To what extent has promotion related with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra state, Nigeria.
- 3) What is the influence of housing provision on teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?
- 4) What effect does medical care has on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?

3.3 Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between salary and promotion on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is significant relationship between salary and promotion on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

3.4 Significance of the Study

The study will be relevant to Anambra state and government of Nigeria in general to identify possible areas teachers in primary schools are lagging behind and improve on salary scheme, timely payment of salaries, promotion, terminal benefits packages and the condition of work environment to motivate teachers to enhance performance.

The study will also be relevant to the teachers in the area of professional development such as seminars, workshops etc. because of the crucial role they stand to play in the educational sector.

The experience at work would lead to quality school management, teaching and learning thereby increasing performance as essential need for attainment of primary education objectives.

The study will help policy makers to make policies to improve on teachers' development programme, motivation and working conditions. This study will add to the volume of literatures on conditions of service and teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area, Anambra state.

More so, the study will be of benefit to the education administrators, teachers, head teachers and other stakeholders who will likely research into similar topic at any point in time in Anambra state and Nigeria and it will go a long way to help future researchers.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Salary as a Correlates of Teachers' Job Performance in Primary Schools

Salary is defined as the bulk and fixed amount of money paid to an employee at the end of the month. It is the compensation given to a work at the end of the month for the service rendered for a person, group or organization. Braton and Gold (2003) defined salary as a *“fixed periodical payment for non-manual employees usually expressed in annual terms, paid per month with generally no additions for productivity”*. This means that money paid as a salary is fixed and is paid in compensation to employee by the employer in return for a work done. Farazmand (2007) observed that employees who receive the same salaries regularly are more likely to perform poorly than employees who receive some incentives. This implies that prompt payment of salaries is a source of motivation to an employee to perform better.

The teachers' performance is directly linked with the quality and quantity of the working condition which the government and the school management offer. The most provided incentives by government involve salaries, transport allowances and housing. In line with this, UNESCO (2006), found that to improve job performance of primary school teachers, government and school administrators need to increase salaries, teachers housing scheme, transport allowances and promotions. However, in schools, payment of salaries are on equitable grounds, based on performance indicators of individuals, derive attraction, participation, commitment and improved performance (Mingat, 2002). Hanushek and Rivkin (2007) found the teacher quality, as measured by teacher's scores on standardized tests and the selectivity of their pupils, also declined during the same time period. Thus, the renewed emphasis on teacher quality forces policy makers, researchers, and school administrators to focus on whether increasing teacher salaries improves teacher quality and pupils' performance. There is some evidence that the impact of salary changes is normally compared to the impact of non-pecuniary factors, for example, teacher working conditions. A motivated worker is easy to spot by his or her ability, dedication, enthusiasm, focus, zeal, and general performance and contribution to organizational objectives and goals. Erdill and Yetkiner (2001) indicated that employee characteristics had to be taken into consideration and that the link between employee-remuneration gaps and labour productivity depends on an employee's position in the remuneration structure. Jirjhan and Kraft (2007) reported that the labour-relations regime and the type of incentive schemes play an important role in determining the sign and magnitude of the link between employee-remuneration gaps and labour productivity.

Scholars have observed that higher salary structure to teacher in primary schools may not improve pupils' academic achievement nor exert teachers to put more efforts in return to compensation for higher salaries (Hanushek, Kain, & Rivkin 1999). Despite available evidence that higher salaries have a positive influence on pupil achievement, some researchers contend that increasing primary school teachers' salaries may not worth the investment. In terms of skill levels, Lallermond (2007), revealed that smaller remuneration gaps are required for higher-skilled teachers if labour output of teaching is to be enhanced. Prendergast (2002) and Turner and Jackson (2009), however, concluded that the relationship between salary payment gap and teacher job performance is stronger when teachers are more skilled. According to them, salary payment for higher-skilled teachers relates with school performance and that more dispersed teachers' salary payment gaps induce them to act in an optimal manner (with higher levels of productivity). Fabiyi (2000) found out that, of all conditions of service, salary is the best predictor of teacher's performance and productivity. In her observation, she expressed that job that offers higher salary would attract more and better qualified personnel than anyone that offers a lower pay. She further added that some teachers' salaries are inadequate, that makes it difficult for them (teachers) to meet their basic necessities of life. In view of this, their salaries when compared to their counterpart with the same qualifications and experience in other sectors of the economy such as doctors, Nurses, Lawyers and bankers etc. can be described as unfavorable. This leads to teachers' dissatisfaction and exhibition of negative attitude towards work. However, this affect graduates who have the zeal for teaching profession to relent and re-sought to work in other sectors of the economy.

On the other hand, Babirye (2011) observed that the extent to which variations in salaries and working conditions translate into difference in the quality of instruction depends importantly on the effectiveness of school personnel policies in hiring and retaining the most effective teachers. He said, the best way to improve the quality of instruction in our primary schools would be to lower barriers to becoming a teacher, such as certification, and to link compensation and career advancement more closely with teachers ability to raise pupils performance. This is sufficient to maintain that proper and prompt pay of salaries of primary school teachers correlates with higher performance but poor salaries to teachers is the reason for poor pupils' performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state. Wherefore, conditions of service as well as teachers' salaries increment, and prompt payment are the major determinants of teachers' effective performance in primary schools. I can go on to say that Anambra state government should improve on teachers' salary and time of remuneration so as to match it with improve teachers' performance in primary school in Onitsha South local government area of the state. Robbins (2003) concludes that, managers and administrators of primary schools should always appreciate, evaluate positively and allocate rewards and incentives more appropriately to their teachers for maximum performance. This shows that salary of teachers influences teachers' job performance in any educational institution.

4.2 Promotion and Teachers Job Performance Primary Schools

Promotion is defined as the act of lifting an employee to a higher position. It is an award for employees who have worked hard, obtained higher qualification and have performed well over time. Promotion is also defined as upward mobility of an employee which changes his present position to one that makes him assume greater responsibility. According to Swinton (2010), promotion tends to put a new life in the individuals and activate their knowledge, skills and their level of commitment to the organizational goals. In the civil service sector promotion plays a key role in motivating and enhancing employees' job performance. Promotion in civil service is symbol of staff recognition, experience, qualification and performance over a period of time (Bell, 2012). Thus, if a worker in an organization is denied being promoted, he or she may be disconnected and consequently leads to labour turnover (Siburian, 2013). He also, suggested that in administering promotion to workers, important factors such as experience, training, skills and intellectual capacity must be considered. He further stressed that striving for promotion may be caused not only by the need for status but also the needs for achievement or recognition of competence. Wherefore, teachers in primary schools need to struggle to perform effectively and efficiently in the classroom and active in-service if they want to be promoted.

Akuoko and Donkor (2012), assert that in awarding promotion to teachers, variables such as teachers training, skills, experiences and intellectual abilities are put in consideration. Thus, teachers awarded promotion in the course of his or her duty in the appropriate time would in no doubt increase satisfaction and job performance. But, despite that it was clearly enshrined in the article 77 section 9 of National policies on Education that promotion opportunities will be created at every educational level to allow for professional growth at each level. However, teachers' promotion in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area, Anambra state and Nigeria in particular has not been properly implemented. Instead of basing promotion of teachers on hard work, higher qualifications obtained and pupils achievements, promotion is today politicized and depend on employees' political connections, favouritism and nepotism. As a result of this, promotions of teachers that does not have political connections or affiliation in primary schools are always delayed and has also not been done on regular basis, this therefore leads to teachers' poor performance.

Other conditions of service include;

4.3 Influence of Housing Provision on Teachers Job Motivation and Performance in Primary Schools

Accommodation or housing allowance is the amount of money paid to teachers to cater for their living expenses for employment situation. Adelabu (2005) investigated teacher motivation and incentives in Nigeria and found out that various state governments had instituted a policy of granting a revolving loan for teachers in order to assist them build their own houses. The study further discovered that the majority of the teachers in primary schools did not receive the housing loans. The researcher recommended that this

policy should be implemented to motivate the teachers to enhance their job performance. In another study, Kadzamira (2006) surveyed teacher motivation and incentives in Malawi. He found out that there was inadequate housing for both primary school teachers. The findings revealed acute shortage of affordable housing within reasonable commuting distance from most schools and this had escalated transport costs for teachers. It was recommended that government should give priority to rural areas in the construction of teachers' houses. The study revealed acute shortage of affordable housing which influence teachers' and their job performance. This implies that lack of housing provision for primary school teachers are the cause of their low performance because they are not motivated.

4.4 Effect of Medical Care on Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Performance in Primary schools

The provisions of medical support to teacher go a long way in motivating and satisfying teachers to work. Chaudhury *et al.* (2004) investigated teacher and health care provides absence in a multi-country study. The researchers found out that poor health and frequent illness of teachers was responsible for teacher absenteeism in most of the primary schools in Sub-Saharan Africa and India. In a related study, Ikenyiri and Ihua-Maduenyi (2011) analyzed teachers' assessment of needs satisfiers as a motivation for teachers' effectiveness in Omoku Rivers state, Nigeria. The study found out that provision of medical and entertainment allowance was a great contributor to teachers' satisfaction and effectiveness in class in primary schools. Whereas the present research is related to these studies, they are geographically apart. In the same way, Afenyadu *et al.*, (2005) carried out a study on improving access to early treatment of malaria in Ghana and the trial was done with primary school teachers as care providers. The study concluded that it is feasible for the health and primary education sectors to work in partnership to improve access to early case detection and adequate management of acute episodes of malaria. The researchers recommended a policy for mandatory commercial blister pre-packaging of anti-malaria's for use by the schools and the general public and collaboration with Ghana Education Service to bring early diagnosis and treatment of malaria a step closer to primary schools and the community. In case studies done in conjunction with the World Bank in Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Uganda and Tanzania, Mulkeen (2005) examined the challenges of teachers of rural schools in Africa. The study revealed that poor health was a common reason given by primary school teachers for early transfer, as ill teachers requested to be posted to urban centres to allow them access to medical services. It was discovered that prevalence of AIDS and lack of medical facilities had made rural postings less attractive to those primary school teachers. Bennell (2005) analyzed information on HIV prevalence and mortality rates among teachers in ten countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, namely South Africa, Botswana, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Swaziland, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia. He concluded that teachers' deaths account for less than twenty per cent of total teacher attrition in most countries and less than ten per cent of total teacher turnover. Teacher mortality rates were

found to be reasonably stable due to behaviour change and increasing access to life prolonging anti-retroviral drug therapies (ART). In conclusion, the teachers in primary schools are not adequate provided with medical care and this result to teachers' unsatisfaction, laziness, absenteeism and irregular class attendance and among others.

5. Theoretical Framework

This study anchored on the theory hierarchy of Needs as its framework. The need theory was developed by Abraham Maslow (1954). The premises of the theory are that people are motivated to fulfill their needs. Maslow claimed that teachers can only put in their best at work when they are healthy, and their basic needs are met. He arranged human needs in five different structures according to order of importance from the lowest to the highest order. That is from ascending order to descending order.

Figure 1.1: Theoretical framework
(Sources: Maslow's need hierarchy: Prasad, 2010)

This diagram in Figure 1.1 illustrates that, Maslow heretically arrange the needs of people from the lowest with physiological needs being the first and satisfy the basic biological needs of people such as food, air to breathe, water, shelter and sleep. Another one following immediately after satisfying the first level need in structure is safety needs. This deals with the need for environmental protection and security of life. That is to be physically safe and secure from danger, harm and assurance for the future. The third level comprises social needs. After satisfaction of physiological and safety needs, social needs are activated. Social needs are concerned with the desire for love, affection and belongingness. Once physiological, safety and social needs have been satisfied, the need for self-esteem is activated. The need for self-esteem is deals with the desire to gain respect and approval by others. Maslow claimed that the highest level of needs is self-actualization. After all the first four needs have been satisfied, people strive for self-actualization. People desire to become all that they are capable of becoming by performing at their maximum levels.

Given the conditions of service such as salary increase, prompt payment of salaries, teachers housing provision, medical care, terminal benefits and among others

are the determinants of teachers job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra state, the theory of hierarchy of needs developed by Abraham Maslow (1954) contribute in motivating and satisfying primary school teachers to improve their performance. The government having seen that these variables are the driven force of productivity; they should give priority attention on them.

6. Methodology

The study used survey research design. The study was limited to Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state. The Onitsha South Local Government Area was created on 29th August 1991. The local government share common boundary with Onitsha North Local Government Area. The local is made up the following communities and villages such as Fegge, Odoakpu, Housing estate and Woliwo Layout. The occupants are mostly traders and civil servants. The population of the study consist of all the 40 Head Teachers and 309 teachers in 40 primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria. The total population is 349. The sample size of the study consists of the 40 Head Teachers and 180 teachers randomly selected from the total population of 349. The total size for the study is 220. The researcher employed a self-developed instrument for data collection for 20-item questionnaires titled, "Conditions of Service as Correlate of Teachers' Job Performance in primary schools" (CSCTJPPS) was designed. The instrument was structured on a four-point scale which sought the opinion of the respondents on four research questions. The face and content validity of the instrument were established by two experts each in the Department of Educational Foundation, Faculty of Education Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University (COOU), Igarim. The reliability of the instrument was determined using SPSS and Cronbach's Alpha with overall index at 0.81 showing that the instrument was reliable for data collection. All the copies of questionnaires administered by the researcher were properly filled, returned and were used for data analysis. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistics. While null hypotheses were tested with chi-square statistics at 0.005 level of significance. Since the items were structured on a four-point Likert scales such as Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree with ranking 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The mean point was established at 2.50. Therefore, any mean score within 2.50 and above were accepted and taken as positive response while any scores less than 2.50 were rejected and taken as negative responses.

6.1 Data Analysis

Research Question 1: How does salary correlates with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores on how salary correlates with teachers’ job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	Salary pay to teachers arouses the skill levels of the primary schools’ teachers to improve job performance.	87	69	59	5	3.06	Accepted
2	Increase teachers’ salaries stimulate higher job performance.	80	89	48	3	3.18	Accepted
3	Regular and prompt payment of salaries enhance teachers’ job performance.	68	66	66	20	2.82	Accepted
4	Delay in payment of teachers’ salary negatively affects teachers job performance.	79	64	67	10	2.96	Accepted
5	Teacher’s job performance is mostly affected when salaries are not paid.	99	62	50	9	3.14	Accepted
7	Payment of leave bonuses increases teachers job performances in primary school.	60	60	40	60	2.54	Accepted
8	Prompt payment of fringe benefits to primary school teachers increases their job performances	65	61	55	39	2.69	Accepted
9	The new salary scale for teachers is sufficient to improve teacher’s job performance in primary school.	58	54	50	58	2.50	Accepted
	Grand Mean					5.72	

Source: Authors analysis of field work.

Table 1 shows the mean scores on how salary correlates with teachers’ job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra sate, Nigeria by the grand mean of 5.72. This by implication means that increment and prompt of salary to teachers enhances teachers’ job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South local government area of Anambra sate, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: To what extent does promotion relates with teachers’ job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra sate, Nigeria.

Table 2: Mean scores on the extent to which promotion relates with teachers’ job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	Mean	Remark
10	Discriminatory promotion of teachers’ effect on their job performance in primary schools.	80	89	48	3	3.18	Accepted
11	Promotion plays a key role in motivating and enhancing teachers job performance in primary school.	98	95	15	12	3.26	Accepted
12	Promotion tends to put a new life in teachers and enhance teachers’ job performance.	68	59	77	16	2.88	Accepted
13	Improvement in the promotion of teachers in primary school enhances their job performance.	60	70	80	10	2.81	Accepted

14	Denial of promotion to a teacher cause disconnection and consequently leads to poor job performance in primary schools.	89	35	90	6	2.94	Accepted
	Grand Mean					3.76	

Source: Authors analysis of field work.

Table 2 identifies the mean scores on the extent to which promotion relates with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigerian by the grand mean of 3.76. This implies that promotion relates with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria to a high extent.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of housing provision on teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean scores on the influence of housing provision on teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
15	Provision of accommodation to teachers improve their job performance in primary school.	80	70	60	10	3.00	Accepted
16	Non housing provision to teachers affects their job productivity.	56	52	49	63	2.45	Rejected
17	Regular provision of accommodation for teachers enhances teachers' satisfaction and job performance in primary schools.	60	69	13	78	2.50	Accepted
	Grand Mean					1.98	

Source: Authors analysis of field work.

Table 3 shows that the mean scores on the influence of housing provision on teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria with grand mean of 1.98. This means that housing provision to teachers does not influence teachers' job motivation and performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: What effect does medical care has on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean scores on effects medical care have on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
18	Government provision of medical care to teaches induces teachers' satisfaction in enhance job performance.	96	81	23	20	3.15	Accepted
19	Irregular medical care made available to teachers in primary does affect the job performance.	65	71	4	80	2.55	Accepted
20	Non provision for medical care to teachers by government affect teachers job performance in primary schools.	60	70	80	10	2.81	Accepted
	Grand Mean					2.12	

Source: Authors analysis of field work.

Table 4 shows the mean scores on the effects medical care have on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria with grand mean of 2.12. This is by implication indicating that medical care does not has any effect on teachers' satisfaction and performance in primary schools in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria,

6.2 Hypotheses Test

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between salary and promotion on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is significant relationship between salary and promotion on teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

The hypothesis is tested using the responses in table1 and table 2 respectively at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5: Test on whether salary and promotion enhance teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Increase teachers' salaries stimulate higher job performance.	80	89	48	3	220
Discriminatory promotion of teachers' effect on their job performance in primary schools.	80	89	48	3	220

Using
$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(o-e)^2}{e}$$

Where

$X^2 =$ Chi square

O = Observed frequency
 E = Expected frequency

$$\text{Salary} = \frac{(80-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(89-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(48-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(3-44)^2}{44}$$

$$= 29.45 + 46.02 + 0.36 + 38.20 = 114.03 / 44 = 2.60$$

$$\text{Promotion} = \frac{(80-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(89-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(48-44)^2}{44} + \frac{(3-44)^2}{44}$$

$$= 29.45 + 46.02 + 0.36 + 38.20 = 114.03 / 44 = 2.60$$

6.3 Finding

X^2 calculated is less than X^2 critical ($2.60 < 3.84$).

Therefore, the study rejects the alternative hypothesis (H_{02}) and accept the null hypotheses (H_{01}) at 0.005 level of significance. This implies that salary and promotion as conditions of services do not correlate with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

7. Conclusion

Based on the findings made from the data analysis, it was concluded that, salary and promotion do not correlate with teachers' job performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria. This is in line with the observation of (Hanushek, Kain & Rivkin 1999) in their study that higher payment salary to teacher in primary schools may not improve pupil's academic achievement nor exert teachers to put more efforts in return to compensation for higher salaries. Again, despite the available evidence that higher salaries have a positive influence on pupils' achievement, the study concluded that that increasing primary school teachers' salaries may not worth the investment they made on the children. Also, teachers need to be motivated from inwardly (intrinsically) to teach the children and not extrinsically because there is no amount of money paid to a teacher that will worth the service they render pupils, the host community and the society at large.

7.1 Recommendations

On the basis of the findings made from data analysis, the following recommendations were made:

- Teachers should be motivated inwardly to teach and improving their job performance not only waiting to be driven by external forces such as salary, promotion, housing provision and as well as medical care. This will better improve the teachers' job performance and pupils' academic performance in primary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria in general.

- Government of Nigeria and Anambra state should encourage teachers in primary schools through adequate conditions of service in other to upgrade educational system and educational output.
- Despite the fact that the study suggested that teachers should first have the love and passion to do the work, government should pay salary to teachers promptly to enable them to attend to their basic needs of life and concentrate on their job for effective delivery. The government and school management should ensure regular promotion of teachers as at when due.
- Regular staff development is an energizer for effective job performance. The government and school management should ensure regular training and re-training of teachers through in-service training, seminars, conferences and workshops towards enhancing job performance.

References

- Abraham Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and Personality*. New York: Harper and Row Publishers.
- Adelabu, M. A. (2005). *Teachers' motivations and incentives in Nigeria*. A paper prepared for an International research project on teachers' motivation and incentives in Africa and South Asia.
- Afenyadu, G. Y., Agyepong, I. A., Barnish, G. and Adjeui, S. (2005). Improving access to early treatment of Malaria. A trial with primary school teachers as care providers. *Tropical medicine and international Health*, 10(10), 1065 - 1072.
- Akande F. B. A. (2014). *Assessment of the relationship between conditions of service and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Kogi State, Nigeria*. An unpublished Theses in the Department of Educational Foundation and Curriculum, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria.
- Akuoko, K. O. and Donkor, D. (2012). Motivation and performance of teachers in selected second cycle institutions in the Ejisu-Juaben municipality, Ashanti, Region, Ghana. *International Journal of Business and Management tomorrow*, 2(9), pp 1-10.
- Ali, R., and Ahmed, M. S. (2009). The Impact of Reward and Recognition Programs on Employee's Motivation and Satisfaction: an Empirical Study. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5(4), 270-279.
- Babirye, J. N. (2011). More support for mothers: a qualitative study on factors affecting immunisation behavior in Kampala, Uganda. *BMC Public Health*, Vol.11 (1) p723
- Bell, B. (2012). *A summary of motivation theories* (pp. 1-26). Retrieved from <http://www.yourcoach.be/blog/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/A-summary-of-motivation-theories1.pdf>
- Bennell, P. (2005). The Impact of the AIDS Epidemic on Teachers in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Development Studies*, vol. 41, issue 3, 440-466

- Braton, J. and Gold, J. (2003). *Human Resource Management: The Theory and practice*. Palgrave Macmillan publishers ltd. Great Britain. (3rd Edition).
- Chaudhury, N., Hammer, J., Kremer, M., Muralidharan, K. and Rogers, F. H. (2004). Missing in Action: Teacher and Health Worker Absence in Developing Countries. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, Vol. 20(1), p91–116.
- Eferayeka, O. A. (1998). *Educational Administration*. Ibadan: Paperback Publishers.
- Erdill, A. and Yetkiner, H. (2001). A Comparative Analysis of Inter-Industry Wage Differences: Industrialized versus developing Countries. *Applied Economics*, 33, 1639-1648.
- Fabiyi, A. I. (2000). *Lecturers job satisfaction and programme in Nigerian Colleges of Education*. In E. D. Fagbamiye and D. O. Durosaro (eds.) *Education and productivity in Nigeria*, Ilorin: Haytee Press and Publishing Company.
- Farazmand, A. (2007). *Strategic personnel Administration: Building and Managing Human Capital for the 21st Century*. Vol 1 Green Wood Publishing Group
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2016). *National Policy on Education'*. Lagos. Report of the committee for the New Education Policy.
- George, J. M. and Jones, G. R. (2008), *Understanding and Managing Organizational Behavior* (5th Ed). New Jersey: Pearson /Prentice Hall.
- Hanushek, E. A. and Rivkin, S. G. (2007). Pay, Working Conditions and Teacher Quality. *The Future of Children*. vol.17 no.1.
- Hanushek, E. A., Kain, J. F. and Rivkin, S. G. (1999). *Do Higher Salaries Buy Better Teachers?* Working Paper W7082. Paper Presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Forms of Compensation.
- Ijaiya, N. Y. S. (1991). *A Guide to Supervision of Instruction*. Ilorin: My Grace Graphic Reproduction Company.
- Jirjhan, U. and Kraft, K. (2007). Intra-firm Wage Dispersion and Firm Performance: is there a Uniform Relationship? *Kyklos*, 60 (2), 231-253.
- Kadzamira, E. C. (2006). Teacher motivation and incentives in Malawi, Center for educational research and training, University of Malawi. (On-line) Available at http://www.dfid.gov.uk/r4d/PDF/Outputs/PolicyStrategy/3888Teacher_motivati_on_Malawi.pdf.
- Karaba, R. (2008). *Making sense of freedom in education: three elements of neoliberal and pragmatic philosophical frameworks*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Miami University, USA.
- Kornblum, Janet (1997-07-29). "AOL dumps new member policy". Archived from [the original](#) on 2013-01-19. Retrieved 2006-12-24.
- Lallermond, T. (2007). *Wage Structure and Firm Productivity in Belgium*. Working Paper 12978, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge.
- Luthans, F. (2005). *Organizational Behaviour* (10th Edition). Boston: Mc Graw Hill/Irwin.
- Mingat, A. and Rakotomalala R. (2002) : *Achieving Universal Primary Education by 2015: A Chance for Every Child*, World Bank.

- Mulkeen, A. (2005). *Teachers for Rural Schools: A Challenge for Africa*. Paper Presented at Ministerial Seminar on Education for Rural People in Africa: Policy Lessons, Option, and Priorities, Addis Ababa: FAO/IIEP/ADEA.
- Neckermann, S. and Kosfeld, M. (2008). *Working for nothing? The effective of non-material awards on employee performance*. Frankfurt Goethe – University, Germany.
- Ogundele, J. O. (2000). *Relationship between Motivation and Teachers' effectiveness*. Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation, University of Ado-Ekiti.
- Osei, M. (2011). *The effect of motivation on employee performance in Ghana education service: a case study of angel educational complex*. Master of Business Administration, KNUST, Kumasi.
- Osinubi, T. S. (2007). Do higher levels of schooling lead to higher returns to education in Nigeria. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 7-1, 157-164.
- Prasad, L. M. (2010). *Principles and Practice of Management*. New Delhi, Sultan Chand & Sons Educational Publishers.
- Prendergast, C. (2002). The Tenuous Trade-off Between Risk and Incentives. *Journal of Public Economy*, 110(5), 1071-1102.
- Rao, D. B. and Kumar, D. N. (2004). *School Teacher Effectiveness*. New Delhi, Discovery Publishing House, pp. 89.
- Robbins, S. P. (2003). *Essentials of Organizational Behavior*. Florida: Pearson education.
- Seniwoliba, A. J. (2013). Teacher motivation and job satisfaction in senior high schools in the Tamale Metropolis of Ghana. *Journal of Education and Review*, 1(9), 181-196.
- Siburian, T. A. (2013). The effect of interpersonal communication, organizational culture, job satisfaction, and achievement motivation to organizational commitment of state high school teacher in the District Humbang Hasundutan, North Sumatera, Indonesia. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(12), 1-15.
- Swinton, L. (2010). Effective business leadership: teamwork and motivation tips. Ezinearticles. Retrieved from <http://ezinearticles.com/?Motivation-Strategies-that-work-and-id=326225>.
- Turner, H. A. and Jackson, D. A. (2009) On the Stability of Wage Differences and Productivity-Based Wage Policies: *An International Analysis*. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 7(1), 1-18.
- Ukeje, J. A. (2007). *Educational reforms in Nigeria*.
<http://www.kantoline.com/publications.Educational.reforms.Nigeria>.
- UNESCO (2006). *Scoralisation Primaire Universelle: Un Objectfe Pourtours*. Document Statistique. MINEDAF VII, UNESCO.
- Venkatesh, V., and Davis, F. D. (2000). *A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal filed studies*. *Management Science*, 46, 186–204. Retrieved from:
http://www.vvenkatesh.com/it/organizations/Theoretical_Models.asp#Con=structdefs.

Verspoor, A. M. (2014). The Quest for Quality: Towards a Learning Community.
Association for the Development of Education in Africa ADEA Newsletter, 16(1):5 – 8.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions, and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions, and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused concerning/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations, and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed, and used in educational, commercial, and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).